

EFFECTS OF HEAT TREATMENT TEMPERATURE ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND MICROSTRUCTURE OF C/C COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Mechanical properties of unidirectional carbon / carbon composites (C/C composites), with mesophase pitch-based carbon fiber as reinforcement and green coke / phenolic resin as matrix precursor, were investigated as a function of microstructural changes. The changes of microstructure with increasing heat treatment temperature (HTT) were evaluated with an aid of micro laser Raman spectroscopy and X-ray diffraction analysis. The flexural strength of the C/C composites was increased bilineally with increasing HTT where a steeper increase at lower than about 2200 K and nearly constant at higher than that was recognized. The turning point at about 2200 K seemed to correspond to the transition of microstructural change within two potential graphitization stages of the matrix.

Keywords: C/C composite, unidirectional composite, heat treatment temperature, mesophase pitch-based carbon fiber, green coke, phenolic resin, micro laser Raman spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction

1. INTRODUCTION

C/C composites are potential candidate structural materials for aerospace and fusion applications [1,2], as they offer excellent resistance to high temperature, superior mechanical properties at high temperature and excellent potential for low induced radio-activity. Together with the development of high performance carbon fibers, improvement of C/C composites have been extensively carried out utilizing variety of precursor systems. However, there are a few systematic studies investigating a relationship between microstructure and mechanical properties of C/C composites [3]. Changes of mechanical properties through microstructural changes of carbon fibers in C/C composites, heat treated at extremely high temperature, are supposed to be an important factor of changes in mechanical properties of C/C composites. The accurate perception, therefore, of the relationship between microstructure and mechanical properties of C/C composites demands the precise investigation into the properties of fibers in composites.

Laser Raman spectroscopy has been shown to be a very effective technique to inspect the degree of graphitization, and numerous studies of various carbon materials have been carried out [4-9]. Micro laser Raman spectroscopy, especially, makes it possible to analyze a microscopic surface area of interest. Thus, by using this technique, it becomes possible to analyze the fibers and

the matrix in C/C composites independently [10]. Raman spectra of most of the carbon materials show double peaks at around 1585 cm^{-1} and 1355 cm^{-1} . The former is known to be the peak of the graphite structure and the latter is to be the peak of defects, and the intensity ratio of the two peaks, $I_{(1585)}/I_{(1355)}$, has been considered to be a good parameter to estimate the degree of graphitization [4].

The objective of this research is to present the effects of graphitization of the fibers and the matrix on the mechanical properties and the fracture behaviors of the C/C composites. The C/C composites were heat treated at temperatures ranged from 1473 K to 2773 K for making a variety of graphitized microstructure. Mechanical properties of the C/C composites were measured by a four point bending test, and supplemental inspections were performed with SEM. The degree of graphitization was evaluated with micro laser Raman spectroscopy and X-ray diffraction analysis.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Materials used were unidirectionally reinforced C/C composites, with mesophase pitch-based carbon fibers as reinforcement and green coke / phenolic resin (the mixture ratio is 80 : 20) as matrix precursor. Prepreg sheets, assembled by a drum winding method, were stacked and hot pressed at 423 K to produce preformed plates. These plates were, then, heat treated at the temperatures shown in Table 1. Heat treatments were performed in argon gas at normal pressure. The temperature elevation speed was 1.7 to 3.3 $\times 10^{-2}$ K/s (1 to 2 K/min) under 1273 K and 1.7 $\times 10^{-1}$ K/s (10 K/min) over 1273 K, and the plates were held at the HTT for 3.6 ks (1 hr.). The fiber volume fraction, V_f , and the density of each materials are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Characteristics of the materials used.

Reinforcement	Mesophase pitch-based carbon fiber (Heat Treatment Temp. : 2473 K)	
Matrix precursor resin	Green Coke : 80 % Phenolic Resin : 20 %	
Heat Treatment Temperature (HTT)	V_f (%)	Density ($\times 10^3 \text{ Kg/m}^3$)
1473 K	45.2	1.62
1673 K	45.1	1.68
1873 K	45.0	1.68
2073 K	45.9	1.71
2273 K	46.6	1.71
2773 K	48.9	1.82

Mechanical properties were measured by a four point bending test. The specimens, with dimension of 1 mm in thickness, 5 mm in width and 40 mm in length, were cut out aligned to the fiber direction parallel to the longitudinal axis of the specimens. Support span, load span and radius of supports were 30 mm, 10 mm and 1 mm, respectively. The tests were carried out in the air at room temperature, and the strain rate was 1.7 $\times 10^{-4}$ /s (cross head speed 0.5 mm/min). The specimens were fractured on the tension side. Flexural strength, σ_{cc} , and fracture strain, ϵ_{cc} , were calculated in the following equations as

$$\sigma_{cc} = P \times L / w \times h^2 \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon_{cc} = D \times h / 0.21 \times L^2 \quad (2)$$

where P is maximum load, L is support span, w is specimen width, h is specimen thickness and D is displacement of the cross head. Duplication number of the test at each HTT was five.

The Raman spectra were measured by a JASCO TRS-600 triplemonochromator and JASCO IMD-1000 multi channel detector, utilizing the 514.5 nm line of an Ar-ion laser with a power of 500 mW. Specimens were cut perpendicular to the fiber axis and then polished. The following measurements were done at the central portion of fiber and at mid-matrix area to avoid the disturbance from non-uniformity of graphitization in fibers and in matrices [11,12]. The diameter of laser spot was about $1 \mu\text{m}$, and the measurements of matrix characteristics were done further than $5 \mu\text{m}$ from interfaces. The illumination duration was 10 s and ten illuminations were repeated for a measurement. The averaged value was obtained from 10 to 20 data points. For the X-ray diffraction analysis, X-ray was radiated to specimens perpendicular to the fiber axis.

3.RESULTS

Flexural strength and fracture strain dependence of C/C composites on HTT are shown in figure 1. The flexural strength increased bilinearly with increasing HTT where a steeper increase at lower than about 2200 K and nearly constant at higher than that were observed. The effect of HTT on fracture strain presented basically the same trend with that of flexural strength, bilinear dependence, with a slightly negative HTT dependence at HTT higher than about 2200 K. The maximum fracture strain of the specimens was 0.40 % at 2273 K. The fracture strain of the same type of fibers in these composites was 0.65 %, as received and 0.53 % after heat treatment at 2773 K for 3.6 ks which is the identical temperature history with the heat treatment of the composites [13]. Because the fracture strain of fibers itself was larger than that of the composites, the fracture strain of the composites was considered to be controlled by fracture strain of the matrix. This model suggests that with increasing HTT up to about 2200 K, fracture strain of matrix monotonically increases and above about 2200 K, it decreases slightly.

Figure 2 shows fracture surfaces of C/C composites. At 1473 K, fiber pull outs are hardly observed with almost null pull out length. This flat and brittle morphology of the fracture surface is consistent with the low flexural strength and the low fracture strain seen in this specimen. With increasing HTT, number of fiber pull outs and pull out length are clearly increased. Another important feature of the fracture surface in the matrix is that the size of fracture unit became smaller and step height to connect each units became larger with increasing HTT. Also the amount of sticking or remaining fragments of the matrix on the surface of fiber pull outs was increased slightly with increasing HTT, which suggested a improvement in interfacial strength. These features are supporting to understand the improvement of fracture toughness, which is considered to restrain catastrophic fracture and lead to increase flexural strength.

Figure 1 Dependence of flexural strength and fracture strain of C/C composites on HTT.

Figure 2 Effect of HTT on fracture morphology of C/C composites.

Micro laser Raman shift spectra are shown in figure 3. For fibers, the peak at around 1585 cm^{-1} was sharpened and the relative peak height at around 1355 cm^{-1} was degraded with increasing HTT, which are known to indicate enhancement of graphitization [14]. For matrices, basically the same phenomena were observed and additionally the 1585 cm^{-1} peak shifted to smaller wave number. This peak shift is also believed to indicate enhancement of graphitization [14].

4.DISCUSSION

Dependence of the intensity ratio, $I_{(1585)}/I_{(1355)}$, of fibers and matrices on HTT is shown in figure 4. With increasing HTT, for fibers, $I_{(1585)}/I_{(1355)}$ showed a slight decrease up to about 2200 K, and a rapid increase over the temperature. The ratios of specimens heat treated above around 2200

Figure 3 Effect of HTT on Raman shift spectra of fibers and matrices in C/C composites.

possibility to interpret the slight degradation of the intensity ratio seen at HTT below about 2200 K. On the other hand, the intensity ratio of fibers in C/C composites after heat treatment at 2273 K became larger than that of as received. The fact that, the HTT of 2273 K is 200 degrees lower than the HTT of the fibers used may indicate the duration of heat treatment at 2273 K of 3.6 ks gives larger impact on microstructural development than the one order of magnitude shorter heat treatment at 2473 K. The intensity ratio of the matrix showed similar trend with that of the fibers, that is, with increasing HTT up to about 2200 K the ratio decreased and then turned to increase steeply above the temperature.

X-ray diffraction spectra of C/C composites are shown in figure 5. Although it is not covered in figure 5, intense 002 peak from graphite was clearly observed in every cases [15]. 100 and 101 peaks seen at 2773 K is not detectable at lower than that temperature, where so called 10 peak, combined peak of 100 and 101 peaks, from turbostratic structure can be identified. As the 10 peak was recognized together with the apparent 002 peak of graphite, the formation of hexagonal graphite planes was supposed to be progressed sufficiently but with insufficient c-axis alignment. And the alignment was improved with increasing HTT enough to detect 100 and 101 peaks

Figure 4 Dependence of $I_{(1585)}/I_{(1355)}$ of fibers and matrices in C/C composites on HTT.

K were larger than that of as received. Carbon fibers are, in general, produced under applied tensile stress in order to develop the graphite structure with hexagonal planes parallel to the fiber axis. Fibers in C/C composites, otherwise, were heated up without applied stress through fabrication of composites and successive heat treatment. Graphite structure of fibers, therefore, was potentially modified rather isotropic by thermal history experienced during the heat treatment. This mechanism about microstructural evolution of graphite structure would be a

Figure 5 Effect of HTT on X-ray diffraction spectra of C/C composites.

Table 2 HTT effect on lattice spacing; d_{002} .

HTT (K)	d_{002} (nm)
1473	0.345
1673	0.346
1873	0.347
2073	0.348
2273	0.345
2773	0.341

Table 3 HTT effect on tensile properties of C fibers.

HTT (K)	Tensile Strength (GPa)	Strain (%)
As Received	3.22	0.65
2273	3.46	0.60
2773	3.65	0.53

separably. Table 2 shows the effect of HTT on lattice spacing of 002, d_{002} . The smaller lattice spacing value seen at higher HTT is consistent with the interpretation about the effect of heat treatment on microstructure development. That is, with increasing HTT, the progress of graphitization is taken place mainly by improvement of alignment along c-axis.

To obtain clear understanding of composite strength, mechanical tests utilizing extracted fibers from composites were successfully applied for SiC/Al [16] and other MMCs. This methodology is not easy to be applied to C/C composites because of the difficulty to extract fibers from composites without damage and as the alternative way Raman spectroscopy measurement of fibers in composites was performed. The results provide some indication about strength change of fibers in C/C composites by heat treatment through microstructure changes but they are insufficient to do quantitative evaluation. Thus, in this paper, effect of heat treatment on fibers not embedded in C/C composites was studied and the results are summarized in Table 3. As was qualitatively expected, with increasing HTT, strength increase and fracture strain decrease were seen. Under the assumption that there would be no significant differences in mechanical properties of fibers in C/C composites and those not embedded in composites, efficiency index of fiber strength usage was defined as

$$E_f = \sigma_{cc} / \sigma_f \times (\epsilon_{cc} / \epsilon_f) \times V_f \quad (3)$$

where E_f is efficiency index of fiber strength usage, σ_f is strength of fiber and ϵ_f is fracture strain of fiber. This index indicates strength of C/C composite as the fraction of the anticipated strength estimated from the fibers at the strain of fracture. This definition stands on the assumption that strength owing to matrix is counted to be negligible small and is not taken into account, and that strength of fibers is proportional to strain in every aspect.

Figure 6 shows the HTT effect on E_f using the data in Table 3. In the calculation, the mechanical properties of fibers at HTT under 2073 K was uniquely represented by those of as received, taking into account the small change shown in figure 4. With increasing HTT, E_f showed quite a little HTT dependence up to about 2200 K and negative dependence over the temperature. The fibers in C/C composites were considered to be damaged through fabrication of composites and successive heat treatment. The self constraint of the matrix and the compressive stress from the matrix to the fibers were considered to increase with increasing HTT. That was supposed to damage the fibers and reduce the number of fibers reinforcing composites "effectively" with increasing HTT.

Figure 6 HTT effect on E_f , efficiency index of fiber strength usage.

The decrease of "effective" V_f , compared with the V_f used in the calculations, induced the decrease of E_f with increasing HTT. That was supposed to be one of the main changes which effected the negative dependence at above the HTT about 2200 K. One other potential effective change was the structural changes of the interface or the matrix close to the interface. There have been many investigations on microstructural changes of C/C composites, for example, preferential graphitization along the fibers, introduced by stress with self constraint of the matrix [17], but correlation between microstructure and mechanical properties of C/C composites has not been clarified yet.

5. CONCLUSION

Mechanical properties of C/C composites were investigated as a function of microstructural changes. The conclusions can be summarized as follows.

- (1) Flexural strength and fracture strain showed different HTT dependence between below and above HTT of about 2200 K. From laser Raman spectroscopy analysis, structural changes of the fibers and the matrix with increasing HTT showed bilinear HTT dependence. The turning point was at about 2200 K, which was similar to that of HTT dependence on mechanical properties of composites.
- (2) Structural changes of the fibers in C/C composites with increasing HTT of composites was observed even below the HTT of the fibers. This fact suggests a potential mechanical properties change under the HTT of fibers.
- (3) Structural changes of fibers and the matrix with increasing HTT was identically measured by micro laser Raman spectroscopy. This technique is expected to be a effective method to clarify the mechanical properties of the fibers and the matrix in composites independently.

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